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RAMONES

Radioactivity Monitoring in Ocean Ecosystems

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Disclaimer

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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ADC	Analog-to-Digital Converter
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application-Specific Integrated Circuit
AttMask	Attention-guided Masking
CPS	Counts per second
LLD	Low-Level Discriminator
MIM	Masked Image Modeling
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NORM	Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
(R)MSE	(Root) Mean Squared Error
ROV	Remotely Operated Vehicle
SoA	State of the art
SUGI	Submarine Gamma Imager
TCP/IP	Transmission Control Protocol / Internet Protocol
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time
ViT	Vision Transformers
DCC	Dose Conversion Coefficient

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Abstract

Among the long-lived radionuclides, those of the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains dominate in contributing to natural radiation exposure of non-human species, with significant dose contribution due to their alpha emissions. The ERICA tool assessed dose rates for living organisms weighing from 10^{-6} kg to 10^3 kg. This study extends ERICA's applicability by using the open-source GATE Monte Carlo platform to compute Dose Conversion Coefficients (DCCs) for smaller microorganisms exposed to alpha particles (internal or external exposures). This research compares GATE's results to ERICA's near its validity limits and explores how DCCs evolve with environmental composition and microorganism size. The open-source GATE MARIM database, including DCC values for 15 alpha-emitting isotopes from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains, is now available with a Python Jupyter notebook interface enabling the calculation of dose rates for microorganisms exposed to natural radioactivity.

1. Introduction

Context

UCA conducted Monte Carlo simulation studies to characterize the natural radiative environment near hydrothermal vents and its impact on microscopic biota. To that purpose, UCA developed realistic simulations of the underwater natural radiative environment using the GATE platform (www.opengatecollaboration.org), studying first the gamma emission from the Uranium decay chain in water and sediments to feed the simulations describing instruments developed in the RAMONES project. Second, the alpha emission's impact on microorganisms was studied.

Structure of the document

Section 3 presents the simulation of natural radioactivity (gamma emission) near hydrothermal vents; the purpose was to study the attenuation of gamma particles coming from ^{222}Rn decay in water and ^{226}Ra decay in sediments. WP4 used these simulations as input to characterize instruments (g-sniffer or SUGI camera) in a realistic environment. Chapter 3 describes the methodology and results obtained for estimating dose rates to microorganisms submitted to natural radioactivity, considering this time the alpha-emitters from the Uranium and Thorium decay chains. To facilitate the interface with the POIS2ON API developed in WP5, a database, GATE MARIM DB, has been implemented for dose assessment of microorganisms exposed to natural alpha-radioactivity.

2. Simulation of radioactivity near hydrothermal vents

The underwater environment was simulated with a 5 x 5 x 4 m cubic volume with a 5 cm thickness seabed made of sediments composed of a mixture of 50% SiO₂ and 50% water with a density equal to 1.8 g cm⁻³. In sediments, ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁴Pb, and ²¹⁴Bi are considered in equilibrium therefore, the same activity was assigned to each of them. In the hydrothermal water column, we considered only the descendants of ²²²Rn, which is present in the gases generated in the water: ²¹⁴Pb and ²¹⁴Bi. The gamma-ray spectra from ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁴Pb, and ²¹⁴Bi in sediments and ²¹⁴Pb and ²¹⁴Bi in water, presented in Figure 1, were used to simulate the energy of source particles. First, we modeled a homogeneous distribution of radioisotopes in a cylinder having a radius of 20 cm. Fluences of gamma particles entering a 30 cm diameter sphere (phase space file) positioned at different depths (5, 10, 15, and 50 cm) at the centre of the water column and 1 m from it have been created (see Figure 2). The phase space files produced were then used as source files for simulating instruments and detectors (mainly the y-sniffer and SUGI camera).

Figure 1 - Gamma-ray spectra from ²²⁶Ra, ²¹⁴Pb, and ²¹⁴Bi, in sediments (left) and in the water column (right).

Figure 2 - Schema of the hydrothermal vent geometry used in the GATE simulations and positions of the phase space files used to recover fluences of gamma particles emitted from homogeneously distributed radioisotopes in water and sediments

Energy spectra of gamma particles at different depths and distances from the hydrothermal water column are presented in Figure 3. At a height of 3 m, and 2.5 m distance from the centre of the column, energies of gamma particles are two orders of magnitude lower than at the seabed surface and centre of the column.

Figure 3 - Energy spectra collected in phase space files located at positions A5 (blue) and F50 (green)

Figure 4 - Complexified source model

We then complexified our model, simulating a homogeneous distribution of radioisotopes in a circular cone having a smaller radius of 25 cm, a higher radius of 2 m, and a height of 4 m (see Figure 4). We collected maps of energy depositions in a voxel-based geometry made of 5 cm side voxels. Energy spectra of gamma particles at different depths and distances from the hydrothermal water column are presented in Figure 5. At a height of 1 m, energies of gamma particles are one order of magnitude lower than at the seabed surface. At a height of 3.5 m, energies are two orders of magnitude lower.

Figure 5 - Energy spectra of gamma particles at different depths and distances from the hydrothermal water column

3. GATE MARIM DB, a Monte Carlo database for dose assessment of microorganisms exposed to natural α -radioactivity

Introduction

The objective was to assess the absorbed dose to microorganisms due to alpha particles in the energy range of natural radioactivity (up to 9 MeV) using the open-source GATE Monte Carlo platform. In the next sections, we detail the dose calculation formalism and the method followed by the GATE platform to achieve the calculation of DCCs beyond the limits of ERICA. We describe the open-source GATE Monte Carlo simulations to Assess the Radiological Impact on Microorganisms (GATE MARIM) database available on GitHub. The database gathers DCC values for 15 alpha-emitter radioisotopes from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains. The user interface to calculate dose rates for microorganisms is then detailed.

In the results section, we present the calculations of DCCs for internal and external exposure and compare them to ERICA's results close to its validity limit. We show the evolution of DCCs as a function of the porosity of the environment surrounding the microorganisms as well as their progression with the size of the microorganisms.

The discussion section explores the consequences of our results. Finally, we draw several perspectives to further improve our description of the effect of natural radiation on aquatic microorganisms.

Material and Methods

Based on the ICRP dosimetric calculation approach, and the methodology of the ERICA (version 2.0) tool, we calculated the dose rates for microorganisms using the following equation:

$$DR = C_{source} \times DCC$$

with

- C_{source} (Bq kg^{-1}): the activity concentration of the radionuclide (in the organism for internal exposure and in the environment for external exposure)
- DCC ($\mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1}): the dose conversion coefficient (for internal or external exposure) that represents the dose rates absorbed per activity concentration in an organism or a medium and is specific to a radionuclide. This parameter can be calculated from Monte Carlo simulation.

The GATE MARIM database collects mean energy deposited per decay in $\text{MeV Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ and DCCs in $\mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} produced for alpha-emitters radioisotopes present in ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains for microorganism diameters ranging from 0.5 to 1200 μm .

Figure 6 summarizes the composition of the database with all parameters (exposures, microorganism diameter, porosity, and radioisotopes) considered. Radioisotopes are homogeneously distributed in the microorganism (made of liquid water) for internal exposure and in a sphere surrounding the microorganism for external exposure.

Figure 6 - Data structure in the GATE MARIM database

When considering external exposure, three different environmental compositions were considered: water, dry sediments (quartz), and a mixture containing 50% of water and 50% of dry sediments. We can describe the mixture using a percentage of porosity to evaluate the proportion of water in a material. The following equation defines the percentage of porosity (in %) as:

$$P(\%) = \frac{V_w}{V_{tot}} \times 100.$$

with:

- V_w : fraction volume of water in the environment,
- V_{tot} : total environment volume.

Atomic compositions in terms of mass fraction and density corresponding to different porosity percentages are described in the following Table:

Porosity	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%
Si	0.3	0.267	0.233	0.2	0.167	0.133	0.1	0.067	0.033
O	0.633	0.6	0.567	0.533	0.5	0.467	0.433	0.4	0.367
H	0.067	0.133	0.2	0.267	0.333	0.4	0.467	0.533	0.6
Density	2.44	2.28	2.12	1.96	1.8	1.64	1.48	1.32	1.16

Pure water is considered to have 100% porosity, and dry sediments have 0% porosity. To specifically study the trend of energy deposited per particle as a function of porosity, we performed simulations using alpha particles emitted from ^{226}Ra decay and porosity between 0% and 100% with 10% steps.

GATE [1]–[3] is an open-source software based on the Geant4 toolkit [4]–[6] that has been in continuous development for more than 20 years focusing on medical imaging, radiotherapy, radioprotection, and dosimetry. Using the Geant4 physics lists, stepping parameters, and energy thresholds enabling the precise tracking of particles, the GATE platform is particularly suited for applications at micro- and nano-metric scales [7]–[9]. In a previous study, co-authors used the GATE platform to simulate absorbed doses to diatoms due to the natural radioactivity present in mineral springs [10]. In this current work, we have generalized its use to create the GATE MARIM database using GATE version 9.4 based on Geant4 version 11.2.

For the calculation of all DCCs in this study, the surrounding environment is modeled with a concentric sphere of radius equivalent to the sum of microorganism radius, and the range of the most energetic alpha particles considered increased by 20%. This way, we ensure to consider an infinite surrounding matrix with dimensions much larger than the particle ranges, as specified by [11]. Radioisotopes are homogeneously distributed in the volume (either in the microorganism for internal exposure or in the spherical environment for external exposure).

We selected the "emstandard_opt4" physics list to ensure high accuracy of electron, hadron, and ion track simulations as recommended by the Geant4 collaboration [12]. Production thresholds for alphas and electrons were set to 0.001 μm inside the microorganism and 0.1 μm in the environment. A maximum step size limiter was fixed to 0.001 μm for alphas and electrons to ensure the simulation of a sufficient number of steps for charged particles at the micrometer scale.

Energy deposited in the microorganism was collected automatically with a DoseActor. The deposited energy per decay $\text{MeV Bq}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ was then obtained by dividing the energy by the number of primary particles generated in the simulation. The statistical uncertainty was kept below 5% for all simulations.

DCC values were then calculated using the following equation:

$$DCC = \frac{E_{dep}}{N} \times \frac{m_s}{m_t} \times C$$

- Edep (MeV): the energy deposited in the microorganism,
- N (Bq s): the number of simulated primary particles,
- m_s (kg): the mass of the source (the mass of the environment for the external exposure and the mass of the microorganism for internal exposure),
- m_t (kg): the mass of the target microorganism,
- C: a unit conversion constant = $5.767 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

First, we calculated DCC values for internal and external exposures to ^{226}Ra using a spherical water geometry to model the microorganism to verify the consistency of DCC values in the limit of use of the ERICA tool (organism diameter of 1240 μm for phytoplankton). For external exposure, we considered the impact of different porosity percentages on DCC values. We then studied the evolution of DCC as a function of microorganism's size for radionuclide alpha-emitters in ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains, for both external and internal exposures.

A Python Jupyter Notebook interface is provided to query the GATE MARIM DB and calculate the dose rate a microorganism receives.

As input parameters, the user can select:

- the density (g cm^{-3}) of the medium describing the environment,
- the radionuclide and its activity in the medium (in Bq kg^{-1} , or Bq m^{-3} , or Bq L^{-1}),
- the internal or external exposure,
- the microorganism diameter (between 0.5 μm and 1200 μm).

DCC values were calculated for 42 different diameters and three different porosity values (0%, 50%, and 100%). For intermediary dimensions, the Python script enables linear interpolations between two consecutive diameters. For intermediary porosity values, an interpolation using a second-order polynomial fit has been applied. An example of the Python interface is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Python interface to query the GATE MARIM database

4. Results and Discussion

DCC calculation with GATE MARIM database

Due to their high Linear Energy Transfer (LET), alpha particles are primarily responsible for dose deposition in microorganisms exposed to natural radioactivity.

We analyzed how the environment porosity, the microorganism size, or the exposure could impact DCC values. To validate our procedure, we first compared the DCC value for internal exposure for the smallest microorganism size (1240 μm in diameter) available in the ERICA tool, finding an excellent agreement.

We then investigated DCC values calculations using the GATE platform for microorganisms' dimensions until 0.5 μm in diameter.

When microorganisms are exposed to external radiation, results reveal that the porosity of the medium plays a key role with 30% differences between 0% and 100% porosity whatever the microorganism dimensions considered. In addition, the more energetic alpha particles a radioisotope emits, the higher the DCC values. The DCC values are 100 times greater for microorganisms with a diameter of 20 μm compared to those with a diameter of 1200 μm, whatever the environment considered, reaching a maximum value of $6.45 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} . Results for external exposure are shown in Figure 8.

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Figure 8 - For external exposure, DCCs for all the alpha-emitters in ^{232}Th and ^{238}U decay chains, are shown for (A) water environment, (C) mixed environment, and (E) sediments. DCCs as a function of the radionuclide considered as source are also shown for (B) water environment, (D) mixed environment, and (F) sediments. Three microorganism diameters are taken into account: 20, 200, and 1200 μm .

Considering internal exposure, we showed that DCC values are increasing with microorganism size. Between 0 and 60 μm , DCC values range between 0 and $1.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} and increase gradually until reaching a plateau and a maximum value of $4.72 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} for ^{212}Po isotope. The DCC values are roughly 10 times greater for microorganisms with a diameter of 1200 μm compared to a smaller microorganism with a diameter of 20 μm whatever the radioisotope considered. Results for internal exposure are depicted in Figure 9.

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Figure 9 - For internal exposure. (A) DCC values as a function of the microorganism diameter for the alpha-emitters in ^{232}Th and ^{238}U decay chains. (B) Zoom on organism diameter below 240 μm . (C) DCC values as a function of the radionuclide considered as a source. Three microorganism diameters are taken into account: 20 μm , 200 μm , and 1200 μm .

Dose rate calculation with the GATE MARIM database

From DCC values in the GATE MARIM database, we proposed to calculate the dose rates for external and internal exposures to ^{222}Rn and ^{226}Ra . External exposure to ^{222}Rn , for a diameter of 20 μm corresponding to the size of a diatom microalgae, has shown a dose rate of $2.79 \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ that is very consistent with the value obtained by Kolovi et al. $2.8 \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$. For an external exposure to ^{226}Ra , our dose rate ($96.53 \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$) is 4.3% higher than the value found by Kolovi et al. ($92,4 \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$).

To go further, we used the range activity concentration of ^{210}Po proposed in Table 7.2 from the IAEA Technical report series N°484 [13] for plankton ($19\text{--}29 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$) to estimate the dose rate to phytoplankton equivalent to a water sphere of 1200 μm in diameter. Using the DCC value of $2.97 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} from the GATE MARIM database, we estimated a maximum dose rate of $86.13 \cdot 10^{-3} \mu\text{Gy h}^{-1}$ per Bq kg^{-1} for an internal exposure to ^{210}Po for phytoplankton.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides a brand-new database of DCC values and energy deposited to microorganisms ranging from 0.5 μm to 1200 μm diameter. The GATE MARIM database is publicly available on GitHub (<https://github.com/lpc-umr6533/marim>) and has been built from the GATE Monte Carlo platform based on the Geant4 toolkit. The major added value of our work was to calculate DCC values for alpha-emitting radionuclides from the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th decay chains for very small microorganisms (from bacteria to phytoplankton) externally or internally exposed to radiation. Our findings pave the way for an accurate calculation of dose rates to microorganisms often sampled near hydrothermal springs to assess the potential role of natural radioactivity in the emergence and evolution of life since Earth's origin.

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